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INHIBITORY EFFECTS OF CALCIUM SULPHATE CONCENTRATIONS ON COOKWARE ALUMINIUM CORROSION IN HIGHLY ACIDIC AND ALKALINE MEDIA AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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Abstract: Corrosion of aluminium cookware is unavoidable. It has been an issue of great concern for decades now due to the toxicological, mutagenic, and carcinogenic effects of the corrosion substances in the human body system, with the ability to cause many chronic ailments. The aim of this paper is to present an inquiry into the inhibitory effects of calcium sulphate as a cheap, worldwide-available, environmentally friendly, biocompatible, and inorganic food substance on corrosion of cookware aluminium in highly acidic and alkaline media. Coupons were produced from the aluminium 6061 alloy as a common cookware aluminium and immersed for 1-3 hours in sequentially treated acidic media of 2.5, 2.7, and 3 pH and alkaline media of 10.5, 10.7, and 11 pH with calcium sulphate (anhydrite) concentrations of 0, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, and 0.35 parts per unit mass of the media at the temperature conditions of 30, 50, and 70°C. Corrosion penetration rates, inhibition efficiencies, and micro-topographical changes of the coupons were evaluated relative to coupons immersed in the untreated media. Results show appreciable corrosion rates of 0.121-1.579 in the acidic and 0.101-1.105 mm/yr in the alkaline media, which increase with the exposure temperatures and durations as well as acidity and alkalinity levels. The highest corrosion inhibition efficiency of 74.34% occurred in the acidic media after a 3-hour immersion in the 2.7-pH medium at 30°C, treated with 0.35 parts per unit mass of the medium, while the highest value in the alkaline media was 72.95% after a 3-hour immersion in the 10.5-pH medium at 30°C, treated with 0.3 parts per unit mass of the medium. SEM micro-topographical analysis indicates that higher concentrations of anhydrite facilitated the coupons' corrosion inhibition in the media by coating formations on them.

Keywords: Cookware aluminium, Corrosion issues, Calcium sulphate, Inorganic substance, Environmentally friendly, Biocompatible, Widely available, Inhibition investigation.

Original Article

INTRODUCTION

The aluminium metal has excellent benefits in food handling due to its low cost, light weight, high temperature tolerance, wide availability, ability to heat and cool quickly, high corrosion resistance, perennial shiny appearance in unpolluted natural environments, and excellent formability into designed kitchenware shapes [1-3]. However, by comparison with many other food-grade metals like stainless steel, aluminium metal has lower strength and hardness integrity and is leachable with a lower level of health safety for use in handling food [1, 3, 4]. There has been much engineering, scientific, and medical concerns about corrosion of aluminium metal since its debut for food handling due to the toxicological, mutagenic and carcinogenic effects of its corrosion ions and other substances in the human body system as free and highly unstable radicals compared to the strongly and stably bound, benign, and less absorbable aluminium ions and other substances that are naturally found in food or water which present no or minimal health risks in human [1, 3, 4, 5]. Leached ions or substances from corroded aluminium can inadvertently find their way into the human body system from time to time through food or water or inhalation and endanger health if their total content exceeds the health-safe guideline value, or if they cause an unacceptable change in the composition of the food or deterioration of its organoleptic properties [1-3, 4, 5]. By European Food Safety (EFSA) and the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) standards, the regulatory limits of critical metals in food-contact aluminum are lead < 0.2 mg/kg, cadmium < 0.5 mg/kg, arsenic < 0.1 mg/kg, and maximum total migration of < 10 mg/dm² [6, 7].

Cookware aluminium refers to a specific category of aluminium alloys, such as Al 1100, 1050, 1060, 1100, 3003, 3105, 5005, 5052, 6061, 6063, 8011, etc., which are specially designed and tested for direct contact with foods and beverages by limiting all elements in it below threshold values for food safety compared to the other aluminium alloys [3, 4, 5, 8-15]. Cookware aluminium alloys are used to produce pots, frying pans, skillets, saucepans, stockpots, baking pans, aluminium foil and wrappings, baking trays, moulds, and food storage containers [7, 8]. Apart from food handling, cookware aluminium alloys have applications in [6,7]:

- i. Electrical systems such as conductors and high-voltage overhead power lines as a lighter and cost-effective alternative to copper.
- ii. Packaging of drugs, cosmetics, and industrial chemicals
- iii. Transportation system components such as aircraft fuselage and wings; automobile engine parts and chassis; and train and ship components, for reduced weight and fuel efficiency improvements.
- iv. Building components, such as window and door frames, curtain walls, roofing, siding, and architectural insulation
- v. The manufacture of various machinery, tools, and equipment parts, including items like ladders, solar panel frames, and robotic components.
- vi. Chemical processing equipment such as tanks and piping.
- vii. Reflective coating for mirrors in telescopes and other optical instruments

The 6061-aluminum alloy is the most popular and cost-efficient of the cookware aluminium alloys. It is used for many parts, from our typical bike to electrical equipment to beverage cans [11, 12]. It is excellently strong, heat-treatable, weldable, formable, machinable, and rust-resistant in comparison to other cookware aluminium alloys [11, 12]. Cookware aluminium or its products are frequently processed, applied, or stored in hot, salty, acidic,

Original Article

and alkaline environments where they undergo various corrosion forms, such as erosion, crevice, pitting, filiform, cavitation, exfoliation, intergranular, galvanic, and microbiologically influenced corrosion. Aluminium cookware tends to resist corrosion well in near-neutral pH environments due to an oxide layer that forms on its surface and protects it from further corrosion [1, 3-5]. Acidic environments of lower than 3 pH, like those encountered in many processing environments or those created by cooking with tomatoes or vinegar, aggravate corrosion of all aluminium metal types with worse effects or consequences than most other environmental types [1-5, 3-5]. Acidic ions, such as chloride, can break down aluminium metal, causing pitting corrosion and forming small holes on its surface. Alkaline conditions of at least 10 pH can accentuate the corrosion of aluminium cookware. In alkaline environments of at least 10 pH, the protective oxide film on the aluminium can become more porous, leading to localized dissolution of the aluminium [1, 3-5]. Furthermore, elevated temperatures and certain foods containing aggressive compounds like allicin or diallyl-disulfide can accelerate the corrosion process of cookware aluminium or its products [15-18].

Cookware aluminium equipment and containers, such as household utensils and foils for wrapping food, are often protected against corrosion or leaching by surface coatings but can be de-coated by corrosion or wear and tear with exposition corrosion effects [1, 3-5, 11]. Apart from the use of suitable coatings, corrosion of cookware aluminium can be principally prevented or mitigated by the use of suitable corrosion inhibitors [1, 19, 20]. The use of corrosion inhibitors is the most versatile and commonly employed technique because it is economical and reliable if properly applied at the optimal concentration for the correct exposure duration. The use of corrosion inhibitors can also be employed to supplement the coating protection to have confidence in the protection [19, 20]. Many organic corrosion inhibitors have been studied and used in very low concentrations of about 0.001-0.1 per unit mass of the environmental media to inhibit corrosion of aluminium alloys with very high efficiencies, but no inhibitor has been found to have all the desirable qualities of an ideal corrosion inhibitor, such as minimal cost and availability everywhere globally with the capability of inhibiting its corrosion by 100% under very minimal or negligible concentration in various possible corrosive media for infinite exposure time [19, 20]. There has therefore been a continued search for better corrosion inhibitors among the numerous inorganic and organic chemical substances, plant, and animal extracts for aluminium cookware in various aqueous media, but the utopia is still far from being achieved [19, 20]. Calcium sulphate is an inorganic mineral substance that is biocompatible with the human body, can be loaded with antibiotics, and is absorbed by the human body over time. It is a white solid in colour and odourless. It has a melting point of 1,400°C, a density of 2.96 g/cm³, and a solubility of 2.63 g/L at 25°C [21-28]. It has various uses in areas such as [21-28]:

- i. Bone grafting, medical casting of bones, and splinting in the medical field.
- ii. Firming agents that help keep foods like canned tomatoes, potatoes, and carrots firm.
- iii. Dough adjustment, firming and stabilizing dough, and providing food for yeast.
- iv. Nutritional supplement due to its high calcium content by adding it to foods and beverages to fortify them with calcium, especially in products like breakfast cereals and plant-based milk alternatives.
- v. Coagulant in the production of tofu to help it to set and be cut-resistant.
- vi. Provision of nutrients for yeast in yeast foods to aid in leavening their yeast.

Original Article

- vii. Key component in building materials in the form known as ‘gypsum’ in drywall and cement, filler in paints, paper, and other products, and in the hemihydrate form to create moulds and cast objects.
- viii. Fertilizer to improve soil structure and reduce alkalinity and provide essential calcium and sulphur for plant growth.

Calcium sulphate occurs in three main forms, namely anhydrite (CaSO_4), gypsum or dihydrate ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), and hemihydrate or plaster of Paris ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$). These forms are distinguished by their water content. Anhydrite contains no water but is the most soluble form in water, while the other two forms contain different levels of water [21-23]. Calcium sulphate is produced as a byproduct of industrial processes such as flue-gas desulfurization, phosphoric acid production, and certain chemical and wastewater treatment processes. It also comes from natural sources like gypsum and anhydrite deposits, which are mined from the earth. It is widely available globally and has an annual production rate of over 260 million tons worldwide, with natural gypsum production at approximately 127 million tons per year. It is sometimes found as an extender component in corrosion inhibition primer pigment systems, such as commercial praseodymium-rich primer, which has been qualified for military use [24-28]. Although calcium sulphate is a food substance that is generally environmentally friendly, including to the human body, and widely available from different production sources, it is not used as a corrosion inhibitor and can even be corrosive to certain metals, although under specific conditions, its sulphate ion is reportedly found to be capable of suppressing corrosion. It is also claimed without clear and sufficient experimental facts from the literature that calcium sulphate can form scale that increases corrosion rates for materials like aluminium alloys and carbon steel in certain environments, but it has little effect on stainless steel in most environments [24-28]. The aim in this paper is to inquire into the inhibitory effects of calcium sulphate (Anhydrite) concentrations of 0-0.35 per unit mass of highly acidic media of 2.5 to 3-pH and alkaline media of 10.5 to 11-pH at temperatures of 30, 50, and 70°C on the corrosion of cookware aluminum in the media for immersion durations of 1-3 hours using the gravimetric weight loss technique and surface microscopy analyses to provide clear experimental facts.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials and equipment

The materials and equipment used for the research work were as follows:

- i. Aluminium 6061 sheet of dimensions 2 mm by 20 mm and length 12,000 mm sourced from a Tower Aluminium depot in Lagos, Nigeria, for producing coupons for the tests.
- ii. The Japanese-made Shimadzu PDA 7000 metal analyser, at the R&D unit of DICON, Kaduna, for ascertaining the status quo of the sourced Al 6061-alloy rod by nominal composition analysis as a cookware aluminium.
- iii. Reagent-grade hydrochloric acid, at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna for preparing the corrosive acidic media for the study.
- iv. Reagent-grade sodium hydroxide at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, for preparing the corrosive alkaline media for the study.
- v. Distilled water at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, for preparing the corrosive media to the required pH levels for the study.

Original Article

- vi. Anhydrite calcium sulphate (CaSO_4) at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, as the test corrosion inhibitor for evaluation.
- vii. Reagent-grade nitric acid at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, for cleaning the coupons.
- viii. Vices at the production workshop of the Department of Mechanical Engineering, NDA, Kaduna, Nigeria, for holding materials or coupons during cutting or preparing them.
- ix. A metric steel rule, metal scribe, and hacksaw at the production workshop of the Department of Mechanical Engineering, NDA, Kaduna, for measuring, marking out, and cutting out coupons to required lengths from the procured Al 6061-alloy rod.
- x. A Mettler analytical weighing balance with accuracy capability of up to 0.001 g at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, for weights of properly cleaned coupons before and after corrosion.
- xi. A grinding machine at the production workshop of the Department of Mechanical Engineering, NDA, Kaduna, for removing burrs and surface marks on coupons during their initial surface preparation.
- xii. A polishing machine at the production workshop of the Department of Mechanical Engineering, NDA, Kaduna, for producing coupons to consistent surface finish.
- xiii. A thermostatically controlled water bath at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, for maintaining the temperature of the prepared corrosive media constant at various required elevated levels for the study.
- xiv. A desiccator at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, for removing moisture on the coupons and from the atmosphere surrounding the coupons
- xv. A digital pH meter at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, for ascertaining the required pH values of the prepared corrosive media.
- xvi. Teflon flasks at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, for containing various calcium-sulphate treated prepared corrosive media for immerse-exposing coupons.
- xvii. An optical microscope at the R&D unit of DICON, Kaduna, for studying the surface micro-topographical patterns of coupons before and after corrosion.
- xviii. Conical flasks at the chemistry laboratory, NDA, Kaduna, for mixing, and storing liquid reagents; and measuring cylinders for accurately measuring the required volumes of liquid reagents for preparing required corrosive media for immerse-exposing coupons.
- xix. A Vernier calliper at the production workshop of the Department of Mechanical Engineering, NDA, Kaduna, for accurately determining the dimensions of coupons during their production to required specifications.
- xx. Pipettes for accurately drawing volumes of reagents to be mixed to required volume and pH levels in preparing the acidic and alkaline media for the study.
- xxi. Sandpapers of 250,300,400 and 600 grit mesh sizes, bought at Kaduna central market for successively polishing coupons.

2.2 Methodology

2.2.1 Sample preparation.

The procured aluminum 6061-alloy sheet was first confirmed to meet the nominal composition requirement by the European Union standard for cookware aluminum by analyzing it using the Japanese-made Shimadzu PDA spectrometer. The confirmed sheet was handsewn into 540 similar coupons of dimensions 15 mm length, 15 mm

Original Article

breadth, and 2 mm thickness. The sewn-out coupons were first scrubbed with a fine-wire brush to remove machining burrs and contaminants on their surfaces. The coupons were successively polished similarly using the 250, 300, 400, and 600 grit papers to remove any roughness and contaminants on their surfaces, rinsed under running water, and dried with a lint-free towel to remove moisture on the surface to an average final dimension of 16 mm length, 16 mm width, and 1.6 mm thickness. Plate 1 shows a sample of the as-sawn-out coupons from the aluminum 6061 alloy sheet.

Plate 1: A top view of a sample of the as-sawn out coupons from Al 6061-alloy sheet

The cleaned coupons were further immersed into 70% nitric acid in a glass beaker for 2 to 3 min, removed and rinsed in distilled water, dried with clean handkerchief, placed in a desiccator for one hour to remove moisture on them, and weighed using the digital Mettler analytical balance to obtain their initial individual and average weights in milligrams. The cleaning process was conducted in accordance with the ASTM G1-25, June 2025, standard practice for preparing, cleaning, and evaluating corrosion test specimens [30]. A desiccator was used to store the prepared coupons in a moisture-free condition prior to the corrosion tests to prevent them from premature or unwanted reactions with the ambient atmospheric moisture. The desiccator was a sealed specialist container that contained silica gel desiccant, which readily absorbed water vapor. Acidic media for the corrosion test were prepared by first pouring 500 milliliters of the reagent-grade hydrochloric acid in a clean Teflon beaker. With a pipette, drops of distilled water were gradually added to the acid in the beaker whilst stirring the content to mix it up and checking its pH with a digital pH meter until a required solution pH value of 2.5 was obtained. The same procedure was repeated to separately prepare the 2.7-pH and 3-pH media. The reagent-grade sodium hydroxide of 99.9% purity was similarly used with distilled water to prepare the alkaline media of 10.5, 10.7, and 11 pH. The prepared acidic and alkaline media were separately stored in large Teflon containers prior to use.

2.2.2 Corrosion tests

The prepared acidic solutions of 2.5, 2.7, and 3 pH and alkaline media of 10.5, 10.7, and 11 pH were each separately drawn with a clean pipette and poured into five different 250-milliliter Teflon containers to equal volumes of 200 milliliters in batches and sequentially treated with 0, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, and 0.35 parts per unit mass of the media using the Mettler analytical weighing balance. This was repeated for each of the other acidic media of 2.7 and 3 pH and all the alkaline media. Three coupons were lifted from the desiccator and immersed in each of the calcium-sulphate-treated acidic and alkaline media in the Teflon containers. Coupons that were immersed

Original Article

in media that were not treated with calcium served as the control coupons for each set of immersion conditions, while coupons in the media treated with various separate calcium sulfate concentrations of 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, and 0.35 per unit mass were used to evaluate the effect of the sulfate concentrations in the respective set of media conditions on the corrosion of the coupons therein relative to the respective control coupons. The calcium-sulphate-treated media in the containers with coupons in them were sequentially maintained in batches at 30°C, 50°C, and 70°C for 1, 2, and 3 hours throughout the immersion duration of coupons in the prepared media using a thermostatically controlled water bath, which housed the media containers under its temperature control. One coupon was removed from each medium set of conditions at the end of 1-hour, 2-hour, and 3-hour immersion durations therein, washed with tap water, and scrubbed with a bristle brush under running tap water to remove the corroded particles, and finally washed with distilled water and dried in the desiccator for one hour in accordance with the ASTM G1-25, 2025, standard practice for preparing, cleaning, and evaluating corrosion test specimens [30]. The final weight in milligrams of the coupon in each case was measured using the digital Mettler analytical balance. The same procedure was separately repeated in batches with each of the acidic media of pH 2.7 and 3.0 and alkaline media of 10.5, 10.7, and 11 maintained at temperatures of 50°C, 50°C, and 70°C and procedurally treated with calcium sulphate concentrations of 0, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, and 0.35 per unit mass. The gravimetric weight loss of each coupon during its immersion time in its corrosive medium was used to calculate its corrosion rate. The weight loss in milligrams was determined by finding the difference between the initial weight and final weight of each coupon before and after its corrosion in the relevant medium in accordance with equation 1.

$$W = W_1 - W_2 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The obtained *W* value of each coupon in its relevant medium set of experimental conditions was used to determine its corrosion penetration rate (CPR) in mm/yr in accordance with equation 2 [29] using the Microsoft Excel software.

$$CPR = \frac{87.6W}{\rho At} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where ρ is the density of the coupon in units of grams per cubic centimetre and equals 2.70 g/cm³, *A* is the average surface exposure area of all the coupons in square centimetres and equals 15.8 cm², and *t* is the exposure time of the coupon in hours for each medium exposure condition. The percentage corrosion inhibition efficiency (*IE*) of the coupon by the calcium sulphate concentration in each medium condition was determined using equation 3 [29].

$$IE = \left(\frac{CPR_a - CPR_p}{CPR_a} \right) 100 \% \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where, *CPR_a* and *CPR_p* are the corrosion rates of the coupon in the absence and presence of a specified calcium sulphate concentration as an inhibitor, respectively.

2.2.3 Micro-topographical examination

In addition to the ASTM G1-25 standard practice [30], the ASTM E 3-11, 2025, standard for the optical microscopy of corrosion specimen analysis [31] was used for microstructural observations of selected uncorroded coupons and corroded coupons under specified corrosion inhibition levels using an optical microscope with an inbuilt camera. Coupons for the study were progressively ground with emery papers of fine grades 220, 320, 400, and 600 grit sizes using water as a coolant. The samples were polished using one-micron-sized alumina powder

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suspended in distilled water, followed by etching in Keller reagent (5% HNO₃ + 3% HCl + 2% HF + 190 ml distilled water) for about 10-30 seconds at room temperature.

Results and Discussions

Results

The nominal composition of the aluminum 6061 alloy, which ascertained it as a cookware aluminum material, is shown in Table 1. The results of the corrosion rates of the coupons after full-immersion exposure durations of 1-3 hours in acidic media of 2.5, 2.7, and 3 pH and alkaline media of 10.5, 10.7, and 11 pH under three different temperature conditions of 30°C, 50°C, and 70°C are presented in Figs. 1a-18a, while the corresponding percentage corrosion inhibition levels by various calcium sulfate concentrations levels of 0, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, and 0.35 per unit mass in the respective media are depicted in Figs. 1b-18b. The SEM-analyzed micro-topographies of the procedurally prepared and uncorroded aluminum coupon, the procedurally prepared and corroded coupon in the most corrosive acidic medium, the procedurally prepared and corroded coupon in the most corrosive alkaline medium, the most corrosion-inhibited coupon in the acidic media, and the most corrosion-inhibited coupon in the alkaline media by the calcium sulphate concentrations are depicted in Plates Ia-Ie, respectively.

Table 1: Nominal composition of the procured Al 6061-alloy for the study

Element	Cr	Si	Mg	Ti	Mn	Fe	Al	Cu	Others
[%] Wt	0.251	0.748	0.915	0.096	0.047	0.615	96.92	0.296	The balance

Fig.1a: CPR of the Al 6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various acidic media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 30°C and pH of 2.5.

Fig.1b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various acidic media of 2.5-pH and temperature of 30°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass of the media

Original Article

Fig.2a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various acidic media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 30°C and pH of 2.7.

Fig.2b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various acidic media of 2.7-pH and temperature of 30°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Fig.3a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various acidic media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 30°C and pH of 3.

Fig.3b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various acidic media of 3-pH and temperature of 30°C for exposure duration of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass of the media

Original Article

Fig.4a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various acidic media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mas at a temperature of 50°C and pH of 2.5

Fig.5a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various acidic media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 50°C and pH of 2.7

Fig.4b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various acidic media of 2.5-pH and temperature of 50°C for exposure duration of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass of the media

Fig.5b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) the of Al-6061 coupons in various acidic media of 2.7-pH and temperature of 50°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass of the media

Original Article

Fig.6a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various acidic media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 50°C and pH of 3

Fig.7a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various acidic media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 70°C and pH of 2.5

Fig.6b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various acidic media of 3-pH and temperature of 50°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass of the media

Fig.7b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various acidic media of 2.5-pH and temperature of 70°C for exposure durations of 1-3

Original Article

hours by 0-0.35 calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass of the media

Fig.8a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various acidic media containing 0-0.35

concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 70°C and pH of 2.7

Fig.8b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in acidic media of 2.7-pH and

temperature of 70°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass of the media

Fig.9a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure times of 1-3 hours in various acidic media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 70°C and pH of 3

Fig.9b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various acidic media of 3-pH and

Original Article

temperature of 70°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass of the media

Fig.10a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various alkaline media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 30°C and pH of 10.5

Fig.10b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various alkaline media of 10.5-pH and temperature of 30°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Fig.11a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various alkaline media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 30°C and pH of 10.7

Original Article

Fig.11b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various alkaline media of 10.7-pH and temperature of 30°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Fig.12a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various alkaline media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 30°C and pH of 11

Fig.12b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various alkaline media of 11-pH and temperature of 30°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Fig. 13a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various alkaline media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 50°C and pH of 10.5

Original Article

Fig.13b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various alkaline media of 10.5-pH and temperature of 50°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Fig.14b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various alkaline media of 10.7-pH and temperature of 50°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Fig.14a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various alkaline media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 50°C and pH of 10.7

Fig.15a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various alkaline media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 50°C and pH of 11

Original Article

Fig.15b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various alkaline media of 11-pH and temperature of 50°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Fig.16b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various alkaline media of 10.7-pH and temperature of 50°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Fig.16a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various alkaline media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 70°C and pH of 10.5

Original Article

Fig.17a: CPR of the Al 6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various alkaline media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 70°C and pH of 10.7

Fig.18a: CPR of the Al-6061 coupons for exposure durations of 1-3 hours in various alkaline media containing 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass at a temperature of 70°C and pH of 11

Fig.17b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency (%) of the Al-6061 coupons in various alkaline media of 10.7-pH and temperature of 70°C for exposure durations of 1-3 hours by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Fig.18b: Corrosion inhibition efficiency of the Al 6061 coupons in various alkaline media of 11-pH at a temperature of 70°C for exposure durations of 1-3 by 0-0.35 concentrations of calcium sulphate per unit mass of the media

Original Article

2000 μm

(a). The as-prepared uncorroded coupon

2000 μm

(b). The most corroded coupon in the acidic media

2000 μm

(d). The most corroded coupon in the alkaline media

2000 μm

(c). The most corrosion-inhibited coupon in the acidic media

2000 μm

(e). The most corrosion-inhibited coupon in the alkaline media

Plate I (a-e): Micro-topography statuesque of the cookware aluminum coupons before and after exposure in the various specified media.

Original Article

Discussion

Table 1 shows that the obtained nominal composition by percentage weights of Cr, Si, Mg, Ti, Mn, Fe, and Cu of the analyzed Al 6061 alloy used for the study are all within the allowable maximum content values of 0-0.35, 0-13.5, 0-11, 0-0.3, 0-4, 0-2, and 0-0.6% for the elements, respectively, according to stipulations by the European Food Law standard for cookware aluminum [4, 5, 7].

From Figs. 1a to 9a, it can be observed that corrosion rates of the cookware aluminum coupons in the acidic media ranged from 1.528 to 0.47 mm/yr. The maximum corrosion rate value of 1.528 mm/yr in the acidic media occurred in the 2.5-pH medium that was maintained at a temperature of 70°C and not treated with calcium sulfate, as can be observed from Fig. 7a, while the minimum corrosion rate value of 0.121 mm/yr occurred after a 3-day immersion duration of the cookware coupon in the 3-pH medium that was maintained at 30°C and treated with 0.35 anhydrite concentration per unit mass of the medium, as can be observed from Fig. 3a. It can also be observed that generally, corrosion rates in the acidic media decrease as the media pH increases from 2.5 to 3, and the calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass in the media increase from 0 to 0.35, but increase as temperature increases from 30 to 70°C. On the other hand, Figs. 1b-9b depict the corrosion inhibition efficiency values for the results in Figs. 1a to 9a, respectively. As can be observed from Figs. 1b-9b, the highest corrosion inhibition efficiency of 74.34% in the acidic media conditions occurred in the medium of 2.7 pH at a temperature condition of 30°C, treated with a calcium sulphate concentration of 0.35 per unit mass of the medium for a coupon immersion duration of 3 days in the medium, as can be observed from Fig. 2b. The corrosion inhibition decreases from the highest value with a decrease in the calcium sulphate concentration to 0 value in all the media conditions that were not treated with calcium sulphate, as can be observed in Figs. 1b-9b. It can also be observed from Figs. 1b-9b that the corrosion inhibition efficiency of the cookware coupons generally decreases with an increase in the operative temperatures of the media but increases with an increase in the coupons' immersion durations of 1-3 hours and calcium sulphate concentration of 0 to 0.35 to a maximum value at the exposure duration of 2 hours in the medium condition with a calcium sulphate concentration of 0.35 per unit mass. It can also be observed from Figs. 1b-9b that the corrosion inhibition of the coupons generally increases from the 2.5-pH media conditions to higher values in the 2.7-pH media conditions and then decreases in the 3-pH media conditions, indicating that higher acidity media increase corrosion rates of cookware aluminum.

From Figs. 10a-18a, corrosion rates of the Al-6061 coupons for the exposure durations of 1-3 hours in alkaline media of 10.5, 10.7, and 11 pH at temperatures of 30, 50, and 70°C decrease from the highest value of 1.105 mm/yr in the 11-pH medium that was not treated with calcium sulfate and maintained at a temperature of 70°C, as can be observed from Fig. 18a, to 0.101 mm/yr in the 10.5-pH medium that was maintained at a temperature of 30°C and treated with 0.35 calcium sulfate concentration per unit mass of the medium at the coupon exposure duration of 3 hours, as can be observed from Fig. 10a. It can also be observed that the corrosion rates in the alkaline media conditions at the pH values are generally less than the values in the acidic media conditions at the pH values of 2.5, 2.7, and 3. The corrosion rates in the alkaline media gradually become less as the media pH decreases from 11 to 10.5 and the calcium sulfate concentrations per unit mass of the media increase from 0 to 0.35 but increase as the temperature of the media increases from 30 to 70°C. On the other hand, Figs. 10b to 18b show that the highest corrosion inhibition efficiency of the coupons in the alkaline media was 72.95% at a 3-hour

Original Article

exposure duration in the 10.5-pH medium that was maintained at a temperature of 30°C and a calcium sulfate treatment concentration of 0.3 per unit mass of the medium, as can be observed from Fig. 13b. The highest corrosion inhibition value of 72.95% decreases to 0 value in all the alkaline media conditions that were treated with no calcium sulfate, as can be observed in Figs. 10b-18b. It can also be observed from Figs. 10b-18b that corrosion inhibition of the coupons in alkaline media of 10.5 to 11 pH by the 0-0.35 calcium sulphate concentrations per unit mass of the media generally decreases with an increase in the operative temperatures of the media but increases with an increase in the exposure durations of 1 to 3 hours of the coupons. It can also be observed from Figs. 10b to 18b that the corrosion inhibition of the coupons generally decreases from the 11-pH medium conditions to higher values in the 10.7-pH medium conditions and then decreases in the 10.5-pH medium conditions.

According to Raviprabha et al. [29], corrosion rates of aluminium and its alloys in hydrochloric acid are high, typically in the range of 0.38 to over 24.66 mm/year, depending heavily on the specific alloy, acid concentration, temperature, and exposure time [31-37]. It is also on record that corrosion rates of aluminium and its alloys in sodium hydroxide are high, with values up to 29.96 mm/yr depending heavily on the specific alloy, sodium hydroxide concentration, temperature, and exposure time [38, 39]. Finally, it can be observed from Figs. 1a-18a that increasing the exposure duration increases corrosion rates of the cookware coupons in the acidic and alkaline media, and for the same exposure duration, elevating the temperature of the acidic and alkaline media increases corrosion rates of the coupons therein relative to similar media conditions. This more or less results in a decrease in corrosion inhibition efficiencies in similar media conditions treated with similar concentrations of the anhydrite, as can be observed in Figs. 1b-18b. In general, an increase in environmental temperature increases the corrosion rate of metals due to the increased kinetic energy of molecules and faster reaction rates [16-18]. The reasons attributed to this increase in temperature are that:

- i. Provides more energy for chemical reactions and causes molecules and ions to move faster and collide more frequently and effectively to increase the electrochemical corrosion reaction rates.
- ii. Enhances the diffusion rates of corrosive agents such as oxygen and ions through the media or protective layers of the coupons, allowing the molecules to reach the coupon surface more quickly.
- iii. Causes thermal expansion of the coupons, which might have widened existing microscopic cracks or fissures on their surfaces, allowing corrosive agents to penetrate deeper and increase their corrosion rates.
- iv. Facilitate the formation of a thermos-galvanic corrosion cell on the coupons' surfaces due to temperature differences across the surfaces in the acidic and alkaline media, such that the hotter spots on their surfaces act as anodes and experience an increase in corrosion rates.
- v. Enhances the capability of some ions, such as chloride, in the acidic media to break down protective natural formations on the coupons, resulting in localized and intensified corrosion, such as crevice or pitting corrosion.

In some cases, an increase in temperature does not cause a significant increase in corrosion rate or slightly reduces it. This is attributed to a decrease in the solubility of some corrosive gases, such as oxygen, in the aqueous media above a certain temperature threshold, leading to a stagnation or *reduction* in the corrosion rate due to inadequate oxygen supply [16-18, 40]. According to Arrhenius's rule, for every 10°C increase in temperature, the rate of

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corrosion can nearly double. However, this is not so from the results depicted in Figs. 1a-18a because the overall effect in the acidic and alkaline media scenarios might be complex and depend on many other unforeseeable variables [16-18, 40].

It can be observed from Figs. 1a-18a and 1b-18b that as the calcium sulphate concentration increases in both the acidic and alkaline media, corrosion rates of the coupons therein decrease and their corrosion inhibition efficiencies increase for the same media conditions. This trend is attributed to the increased adsorption of the sulphate molecules onto the surface, resulting in more compact and stable protective film formation on the coupons with physical separation of the coupons from the media conditions and blockage of active corrosion sites.

From Plate Ia, it can be seen that the micro-topography of the as-prepared and uncorroded coupon looks smoother, more uniform, shinier, brighter, and more polished than all the corroded coupons in the most corrosive acidic and alkaline media and the most corrosion-inhibited coupons in the acidic and alkaline media shown in Plates Ib-Ie. The micro-topography of the most corroded coupon in the acidic media looks roughest, least uniform, least shiny, least bright, and least polished with signs of deeper pits or craters and greater flaking and blistering than all the coupons, as can be observed from Plates Ia-Ie. The micro-topography of the most corrosion-inhibited coupon in the acidic media, as can be seen from Plate ID, looks smoother and more uniform than the most corroded coupons in both the acidic and alkaline media but less so in quality than the most corrosion-inhibited coupon in the alkaline media. This indicates that differences in corrosion levels of the aluminum coupons manifested in their surface deterioration levels and the levels of corrosion inhibition by the calcium sulfate concentrations in the media. The micro-topography of the most corrosion-inhibited coupon in the alkaline media, however, has an edge in better surface roughness leveling, uniformity, and consistency than the microstructure of the most corrosion-inhibited coupon in the acidic media.

The usual corrosion inhibitor concentrations for aluminum metal vary significantly depending on the specific inhibitor and the pH level of the environment [41-47]. Generally, inhibitor concentration ranges are often in the parts per million (ppm) for many synthetic organic and green inhibitors, or up to several percentage points for some inorganic compounds. In acidic media such as HCl and H₂SO₄, organic compounds are frequently used as inhibitors. Many effective organic inhibitors can be used at very low concentrations of 0.01 to 1% in acidic and alkaline environments to inhibit corrosion of aluminum metal with very high corrosion inhibition efficiencies of even over 90% in many cases. However, the corrosion inhibition efficiency of the cookware aluminum coupons by calcium sulphate concentrations of 20-35% in the acidic and alkaline media used in this study is only up to 74.24% and seen to be very low. This indicates that for the highest comparable corrosion inhibition of cookware aluminum in acidic and alkaline media with organic corrosion inhibitors, the calcium sulphate concentration in the media needs to be greater than 35%, and this may not make calcium sulphate an economical corrosion inhibitor for the cookware aluminum purpose. This indicates that calcium sulfate can only be more reliably used to protect cookware aluminum in acidic and alkaline media when in very high concentrations of the media [41-47].

4.0 CONCLUSION

The inhibitory effects of calcium sulphate, a worldwide-available, cheap, and environmentally friendly, biocompatible, inorganic food substance of diverse applications, on the corrosion of cookware aluminium in

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highly acidic and alkaline media at temperatures of 30, 50, and 70°C have been systematically investigated experimentally. The investigation results indicate that:

- i. The use of corrosion inhibitors and research progress on the subject have been a major and versatile method of mitigating corrosion of cookware aluminum or supplementing its protective coating for greater protection
- ii. Appreciable corrosion inhibition levels of cookware aluminum corrosion in in alkaline media with 2.5-3 pH and 10.5-11 pH, by calcium sulphate concentrations of 20-35% that increase with the concentrations, exposure durations of the aluminum in the media, and decrease in the media temperature.
- iii. Calcium sulfate concentrations facilitate corrosion inhibition of cookware aluminum in the media by coating formations on its surface, which separate its surface from the media corrodent.
- iv. In comparison with very low organic corrosion inhibitor concentrations of 0.01 to 1% that are usually used in acidic and alkaline environments to inhibit corrosion of aluminum metal with very high corrosion inhibition efficiencies that can be over 90% in many cases, the corrosion inhibition efficiencies of the cookware aluminum coupons by calcium sulfate concentrations of 20-35% in the acidic and alkaline media used in this study are very low.
- v. For the highest comparable corrosion inhibition of cookware aluminum in acidic and alkaline media with many organic corrosion inhibitors, the calcium sulphate concentration in the media needs to be greater than 35%, and this may not make calcium sulphate comparatively economical with organic corrosion inhibitors for cookware aluminum corrosion inhibition. This indicates that calcium sulfate can only be more reliably used in comparison with organic corrosion inhibitors to protect cookware aluminum in acidic and alkaline media when in very high concentrations of the media.

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